

An Islamic Module for Internship Progressiveness: Parental Involvement and Professional Trends & Practices in Higher Education

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Abstract:

Education is the most important phase in human life. It begins from teaching of parents to tutors and then institutions to society. Islam stresses that parents are the fore-most; oldest and ever-remaining character in learning and developmental process and modern research admitted that they have a very crucial role in human development. Capitalist behaviour camouflaged this crucial role to conceal the mistakes and emotional deficiency of educational management. Administration put a board "No parents beyond this point" to stop communication of parents with children and teachers. They invaded many practices in educational administrative circle to snub the parents so that they can draw more financial benefits in the name of modern and quality education. Modern research and worthy teaching of Semitic religions are bluntly saying that involvement of parents is very productive and effective in not only general learning process but also in professional development. Parents, especially in Eastern countries, are sufficiently unaware with the practices of their involvement in Professional Development Process (PDP) of their children specifically in Higher education. Research in Education developed many modules of parental involvement in educational spheres like Parent Teacher Association (PTA), (HSP), (SEs), (HVS), (HUA) and Parents-Student Internship Project (P-SIP). This article discussed critically and analytically the importance of P-SIP on Islamic basis and its module to convey the wholesome picture of parental involvement in learning process for professional development in higher education. Resultantly, any institution can adopt this module to implement it into its system for a productive learning output.

Keywords:

Parental Involvement, Professional Development, Trends & Practices, PDP, PTA, HSP, SE, HVS, HUA, P-SIP

Introduction:

Teaching from parents is the pioneer' in the area of common and specialized teaching and learning for children's learning life (Wise, 2005). And finally 'ethnicities, traditions and attitudes have been an ever remaining stamp upon the mental statuses of children, adults' behavior, knowledge and attitude. (Jayakumar, 2002, p.96)

Parents, in a broad sense, are a family as recognized by (UNO General Assembly, 1997, P.1) that family is a basic institution for learning in community.

Parents are the oldest and ever-lasting character in learning and developing process. It is admitted by the advanced research that parents have a very crucial role in students learning process.

Bertrand Russel said about the importance of a family in educational spheres. The family is the most ancient human institution. It is older than government, older than property, older even than man (Russel, 2002, p.164). This has the most important role for the development of education. "And it is parental attitude."

Quran describes the status of parents by the decree of Allah almighty for good treatment without any reward with parents immediately after the decree of abiding the laws of Himself. It further explained that children should not say even 'uff' and do not repel them (Quran 17:23).

Trends and Practices:

Earning and emerging trend of capitalist life de-tracked social educational behaviour to conceal the mistakes and 'emotional deficiency, in the form of Anxiety, of educational management' (James, 2004, p.266). Educational management put the parents at length from students under the veil of professional efficiency. Sign board "No parents beyond this point" (Vincent, 2004, p.1) in educational institutions build a gap between teachers and parents. The gap is harmful and deteriorating for teaching and learning efficiency of students especially in higher education level.

Need of Students' Age in Higher Education:

Parents' approach is vital for learning behaviors of their students especially all aspects of higher educational institutions because the age is very emotional and need sincere and emotionally experienced hands to mend, cover and help them (Gootman, 2001, p.16). Besides that a student is existing with their parents and they have to follow their parents' order particularly in eastern communities and additionally they are reliant on their parentages (Churchill, 2011, p.16).

The importance of parents in educational sphere is crucial and need of parent-teacher relations to understand the problem of the low educational interest rate especially in Higher Education sphere.

Modern research and worthy teaching of Semitic religions are also bluntly saying that 'involvement of parents is very productive and effective' in not only general learning process but also in 'professional development' (Murphy, 2001, p.214).

The Basic Theme of the Study:

In the last ten years or so, parentages have suited in learning process in Pakistan at school level. Parents are now an un-deniable power in the field of instruction and erudition in higher education also. "Parents and the community that have increased the expectations of education and are becoming more demanding of better performance for their children" (Cheng, 2007, p.255). Parents' presence in many institutions and classrooms indicate the trend to understand the importance of their character in accompanying their student's learning and Professional Development Procedure (PDP).

The evidence is available from personal testimony of parents, teachers and students by surveys, questionnaires and the results of many projects that how effects came to light in this response. (Townsend, 2007, p.20)

In this focus there are several points which have been described here for the importance of parents in educational fields.

1. The influence of parents on their children's development and learning.
2. Description of home-Institution relations.
3. Encouragement of an effective working

relationship between parents, students and teachers.

4. Importance of maintenance and endurance of parent-student working relationship.
5. Solid development of learning relations in the educational legislation and contemporary contexts.
6. Show the positive future in terms of home-institution links. (Sackney, 2007, p.195)

Effectiveness enlargement through parental contribution in teaching and learning process has been asserted by highly committed and organized researchers all over the globe is witnessed through the above reference of Canadian research.

Significances of the Study:

This study is to look at the contribution and influence of parents from as many angles as possible just as one might look into a prism and see different lights and colors reflected simultaneously and accelerate the importance of Parents Fellowship Project Module specifically.

1. To look at the kinds of contacts among parents, institutions and teachers.
2. To search out the original role of Parents.
3. To illustrate how parents can become a forceful and effective co-ordinate in young's education.
4. To explore the some issues about sharing the responsibility a/young's educational decisions.
5. To see how parents can create caring environments at home that's provide the contexts to young's development and learning.
6. To examine the experience and skill of teachers to joint enterprises with parents.
7. To know about parental action and what they do for their students.
8. To understand the importance of parents for educational institutions.
9. To explore the most effective and result oriented way for qualitative and efficient learning in Higher Education Level.

Acquired Fields

Parent's rights:

We know that parents have fundamental rights to be participant in some educational decision-making powers with educational institutions and governing bodies on receiving reports form institutions about their children's educational progress (Shulman, 2014, p.2).

The notion of privileges can be acted as a facilitator to safeguard that not only parentages recognize their freedoms but also they assurance that the privileges will have been articulated.

وَآخِضْ لَهُمَا جَنَاحَ الذَّلِيلِ مِنَ الرَّحْمَةِ وَقُلْ رَبِّ ارْحَمْهُمَا كَمَا رَبَّيَانِي صَغِيرًا ﴿٢٤﴾

Islamic perspective illustrates the treatment of youth with their parents as humble as they treat humbly and softly with their children when they were small as worthless. (Quran 17:24)

Insurances:

Typically, enablement denotes to the ways that the conclusions of realizing and uttering requirements, desires and privileges to ensure that the parental latent influence to impact instructive strategy in ensuring that parentage's opinions are perceived in relativity to the edification of their higher education students (Barnes, 2011, p.145).

Equality:

Many writers, researchers, practitioners and parents has been addressed the concept of "parents as partners in educational matters" (Mitchell, 2011, p.151), (Jones, 2004, p.87) (Galloway, 2013, p.69).

Participation:

Participation reposes on the evidence that every involved parent is donating and partaking evidence, articulating and finally satisfying the errands for activities and conclusions. Parental participation is matched with all of these contributions in Educational spheres (Craig, 1998, p.122).

Parent's problems:

(a) General problems;

There are sufficient evidences that there is a majority of parents who do not to care their young because those;

- (a) are over whelmed by stressful life-events.
- (b) are under pressure for financial problems.
- (c) have not their self-knowledge of affirmative institutionalization to overwhelmed the

qualms and disquiets about higher education and professors (Patterson, 2014, p.208)

Expectation problems;

The expectations of single parents and its results are as that “Single parents who live along with their low expectations for their children’s performance in first-grade and these lower expectations account in part for the poorer performance in first graders and this poor performance goes on.” (Thompson, 2002, p.241)

And in another focus narrated about expectations of compound families is “Compound families have compound expectations for their children so students became confused by their future” (Guald, 2017).

Parental Involvement and Higher Educational Trends

Researchers provided brief fundamental benefits through the involvement of parents in educational institutions.

1. Produces such parents who have knowledge about educational needs.
2. Providing of extra personnel and human resources for learning.
3. Giving students an additional operative erudition atmosphere, it becomes conceivable by an amplified Higher education proportion.
4. Benevolent parentage innovative vision and indulgent round their students, as parents shape bonds between home Parental education and institutional culture. (Hornby, 2011, p.9)

The benefits of parental involvement for educational spherical concerned through parents are described in simplified words as under:-

- “1. They can help their own students as “Counsellor, friends and Supporters”.
2. They can help the educational institution as “learners/trainers/advises”
3. They can meet some of their own needs as “volunteers/Aides or Assistants” (Fine, 2014, p.231).

He draws attention to and synthesizes a number of recommendations in several government

reports on education and students health which call for closer working links between parents and professionals on the grounds that this is in student's best interests.

Such involvement provides the opportunities for parents themselves to learn, to grow, to explore the possibilities, to come familiar with organizations such as higher educational institutions and local educational authorities to challenge the existing structures and traditions.

Solutions:

In many of the projects, parental involvement in a variety of forms was paramount, nevertheless its methods and practices have been very influential (Jeynes, 2011, p.112).

Parental attitude for the best of their children can be described as ‘Involvement of parents, mentioned by researchers, discovered the effectiveness of parents as educators and trainers in a range of early learning and opportunities of behavioral change primarily at home but at educational institution too’ (Hornby, 2011, p.56).

A researcher evaluated the parental involvement in these words, ‘Across the procedure of patting and remaining separate of an higher learning program through this their students endure contributor, numerous parentages grow additional erudite, self-assuredness, thoughtfulness of educational field and improved fortification to inquire queries and encounter, in a word, parents become Effective (Jeynes, 2011, p.151).

It has been proved that research and practice in this area, has combined to provide not only the 'proof about the effectiveness of such collaborations can also be evaluated its underpinning philosophy and rational effects.

Importance of parental involvement in educational spheres has been displayed by the under given flow chart.

Suggestions:

1. Parent Teacher Association (PTA)
2. Home Institution Project (HIP)
3. Second Educators (SEs)
4. Home Visiting Scheme (HVS)
5. Home University Agreement (HUA)
6. Parents-Student Internship Project (P-SIP)

The presentation is the first step of series of presentation of these modules which are developed for the effective output of higher educational institutions. Parent Teacher Association (PTA), Home Institution Project (HIP), second Educations (SEs), Home Visiting Scheme (HVS), Home University Agreement (HUA) and Parents-Student Internship Project (P-SIP) are developed modules for a brief explanation and later implementation.

Institutions of higher education can adopt any one or more modules to implement into their system for an effective Professional Development Process (PDP).

Above mentioned modules are already discussed and presented in somewhat explanations but Parents-Student Internship Project (P-SIP) is the latest one which needs an explanation.

Parents-Student Internship Project (P-SIP):

Internship is a position containing a specific time limited period to attain work experience in a real professional atmosphere relating to the achieved qualification. Almost all the students of higher education have internship need to satisfy the requirements of their degree.

Families or parents are the basic unit for generations of human being. In present era, such atmosphere has/is being developed that parents are

becoming a neglecting and unimportant part of life. This trend is crushing the wholesome structure of societies to defect the original development- the human development.

P-SIP is based on that crucial vision to save the parental statues in society and highlight the importance and efficiency of the structure. P-SIP has specific aims and objectives which are as vital as the food for human being.

Social Atmosphere & Internship Trends:

Parents are the centre of young and olds' lives but a social atmospheric trend pushing the cultures towards negligibility of parent ship. Love, affection, emotional affiliation, efforts for successful life, sacrifice and many positive deeds are the property of Parent ship.

Presently, there is a gap between students at higher educational institutions and their parents which is hindrance to understand the love and affection of parents and responsibilities of these students for their future children. On the other side, Last Prophet Muhammad صلى الله عليه وآله واصحابه stressed on love and service of parents in the following words in (Sahih Muslim, 1978:4 & 2551)

باب رَغِمَ أَنْفٌ مَنْ أَدْرَكَ أَبَوَيْهِ أَوْ أَحَدَهُمَا عِنْدَ الْكِبَرِ فَلَمْ يَدْخُلِ الْحَمْدَ:

In present higher educational structure, students are sent to normally unknown and unfamiliar organizations, offices, institutions and atmospheres to complete their internship period. They face many problems, hurdles and unknown situations which creates unsatisfactory achievement experience.

Disadvantages of Prevalent Internship Systems:

- Internees are treated as Assistant and sometime as even slaves
- Chances to learn fully or exactly are not given to internees
- Generally Internees spent their internship time in getting coffees, making copies and running errands (Karrera, 2017, Careeraddict.com)
- Organizations and employers consider the internship as a waste of time
- Internship deviate/dispel the attentions of actual employees from their tasks

- Some managers give mindless tasks to internees
- Generally, internees face humiliating and ignoring behaviour from officials
- No individual attention due to huge number of internees at the same organization
- Generally, internee has to relocate due to far-place internship which is a problematic phase
- Unsatisfactory, unacceptable, sub-standard, inadequate and disappointing situations
- Normally and mostly, it is a kill of time.
- Internee feels disrespect and botheration during internships (Admin, 2015, TheEmployable.com)

Module of (P-SIP):

P-SIP changes the focus of internship from professionalism to personalization. It provides personal attentions, sincere efforts for skill development and result oriented participation of stakeholders.

In P-SIP, higher educational institutions send the students to their own parents for internship. If the parents have not same field of professional attachment then the parents will send their siblings to their trusted relatives and friends within their same professions to get work experience during their internships.

The detailed module needs 7 consecutive lectures to present.

Merits' Overview of (P-SIP):

Parental attachment, supervision, affection and sincerity enhance the effectiveness and sure skill development in internee. Overview of some merits can be displayed as under:

- Pleasant experience with parents in professional atmosphere
- Real Work experience in a short time period
- Respective, affection ting and sincere atmosphere
- Gifts and achievement awards winning probabilities
- Save and honourable environment for especially female internees
- First working experience will be memorable and golden work experience

- Sure chances to learn original and actual skills and tactics in wholesome manner
- Start of trustworthy relations and contacts in professional line
- Real help for becoming more confident and professional in the start of professional life.
- Fool proof way to accelerate the CV of an internee
- Open opportunity to share learning experiences in higher educational institution
- Parents or their affiliates are well informed with the behaviours and personalities of the internees so they will train and guide them on actual pattern
- Close coordination by the managers and officials due to their own interest in the future of internee
- Best way to increase the market value of the internee because internees' manager will increase the value of internee due to their own concern
- The manager will guide and train the internee in right and perfect mind-set
- Parental affiliation and connection in internees internship is also a solid reason of internees' jobs

Results / Recommendation:

In the view of above explanations, it is resulted and, therefore, recommended that higher education institutions should accumulate or replace the prevalent internship systems with the Parents-Student Internship Project P-SIP implementation.

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